

CLEAN OR DIRTY INTERFACES? THE INFLUENCE OF INTERFACIAL MORPHOLOGY ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF MMCs

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ABSTRACT

The tensile properties and metal/ceramic interfacial morphologies of spray-deposited Al-Mg reinforced with either SiC_p^{ox} or $\text{SiC}_p^{\text{non-ox}}$ are characterised for the as extruded and heat-treated conditions. In both materials the heat treatment results in an increase in elastic modulus but negligible change in proof stress. TEM observations of the corresponding changes in microstructure indicate that these enhanced elastic properties are due to an improved load transfer between the phases, which results for Al-Mg/ SiC_p^{ox} from an interactive diffusional process, and for Al-Mg/ $\text{SiC}_p^{\text{non-ox}}$ from the production of interfacial Al_4C_3 particles that are "keyed in" to both phases.

INTRODUCTION

The strength of the interfacial bond has long been regarded as crucial to the bulk mechanical behaviour of composite materials¹. A variety of techniques has thus been used to examine the microstructure of the interfacial region, and the desirability of a "clean" interface (precipitate- and reaction-free) in MMCs has frequently been asserted. However, specific correlations of this microstructure with the macroscopic composite mechanical behaviour are as yet inconclusive, both because of the generally heterogeneously dirty state of the interfaces in as produced MMCs, and because of the subsequent difficulty in altering the interface condition without changing the mechanical characteristics of the matrix.

In order to address this problem unambiguously, we must consider a composite system which allows a controlled modification of the interface without thereby significantly affecting the properties of the matrix; for aluminium-based composites this criterion is most nearly fulfilled by spray-deposited Al-Mg/ SiC_p . As a consequence of the short molten metal/reinforcement contact times inherent to the process¹, spray deposition allows the production of particulate reinforced composites with very "clean" interfaces (see below and ref²) which can subsequently be modified by suitable heat treatments. The binary Al-Mg matrix has been chosen for this investigation for the following reasons: its mechanical properties should be only marginally affected by heat treatment as it remains a solid solution throughout the relevant temperature range; if this matrix is reinforced with one of two forms of SiC, one coated with an oxide layer and the other chemically cleaned, then with the former the magnesium will oxidise at the interface during high temperature processing³, and with the latter we can expect some reaction involving production of Al_4C_3 ⁴. Since both these processes will modify the nature of the interface bond, a comparison of the microstructural and mechanical changes with heat treatment in the two systems should provide the information required.

We describe here our work on the TEM characterisation of the SiC/matrix interfaces after different heat treatments in Al-Mg reinforced with either chemically cleaned or oxidised SiC particles, correlating these observations with elastic modulus and yield stress data obtained from mechanical tests.

EXPERIMENTAL

We have examined two composite materials: Al-1.9%Mg reinforced with 14% volume of oxidised SiC particles (F600 grit), and the same alloy reinforced with the same size distribution of chemically cleaned particles (at 16% volume). These volume fractions were measured both by chemical analysis and using an optical image analyser. The latter method also allowed a measurement of the effective aspect ratio of the particles in the extruded composites, which proved to be about 1.7 for both materials. The SiC particles were in general evenly distributed throughout the composite but,

because Al-Mg is a particularly difficult alloy to spray, there was still some residual porosity (a couple of percent) in the matrix, though this would be expected to affect the mechanical response of the two systems equally.

The interface microstructure and corresponding mechanical response were characterised for four different composite conditions: Al-Mg/SiC_p^{non-ox} and Al-Mg/SiC_p^{ox} as extruded, and the two materials after 20hrs at 625°C. The mechanical data detailed below were obtained using a "push-pull" rig on a servo-hydraulic testing machine (100kN Mand). It was possible, after applying low load fatigue cycles, to obtain consistent and reproducible modulus measurements from such tests⁵, as well as proof stress and Bauschinger effect measurements. Thin foils for electron microscopy were prepared using standard ion beam milling techniques⁶, which enable approximately even thinning of both phases of the composite.

MECHANICAL TESTING RESULTS

Figure 1 is a typical mechanical testing curve, in this case for Al-Mg/SiC_p^{ox}, demonstrating the method by which the elastic modulus and 0.1% proportional limit were measured. The composite microyields from a very low stress, rendering it impossible to determine the elastic properties accurately from the initial deformation curve. In consequence, we have used the unloading curves and a specific low load fatigue procedure (see figure caption and ref⁵) to measure the elastic modulus, and compared this slope with the initial loading curve to obtain a 0.1% yield stress.

Measurements of the elastic modulus and 0.1% proof stress for tests both at room temperature and under liquid nitrogen are presented in table 1, along with modulus values predicted from an Eshelby-based model⁵. Such a model implicitly assumes perfect bonding between the two phases of the composite, and has been demonstrated to give good predictions of elastic properties in other work on short fibre MMCs^{5,7}. The magnitude of the difference between these predicted values and the measured moduli cannot be explained solely by the observed porosity but must also indicate poor interfacial bonding.

Table 1 - Mechanical testing data

Specimen	Heat treatment	Modulus measurements (GPa)		0.1% Proof stresses(MPa)	
		(RT)	(77K)	(RT)	(77K)
Al-Mg/SiC _p ^{non-ox}	none	77.6	88.6	85	115
Al-Mg/SiC _p ^{non-ox}	20hrs at 625°C	83.1	93.8	85	108
Al-Mg/SiC _p ^{ox}	none	76.2	88.5	75	105
Al-Mg/SiC _p ^{ox}	20hrs at 625°C	79.9	91.4	75	105

The above data are averages of at least two experiments, the experimental scatter of data being about +/-1% for the modulus measurements. Predicted modulus values for the two materials at room temperature were 90.6 GPa (Al-Mg/16% SiC_p^{non-ox}) and 87.7 GPa (Al-Mg/ 14%SiC_p^{ox}).

It is important to note that the difference between the room temperature and 77K modulus measurements can largely be attributed to a corresponding variation in the elastic modulus of aluminium alloys. Aluminium's modulus is reported to be about 70GPa at 300K, rising to about 79GPa at 77K⁸; the increase in SiC's modulus over this temperature range is difficult to ascertain accurately (as indeed is its modulus at any temperature), though it is definitely much smaller than that for Al⁹. According to our Eshelby-based model, any change in matrix elastic modulus in the aluminium/SiC system should be reflected by an approximately equal change in the composite's elastic modulus, which is consistent with this data. Similarly, the general increase in yield stress between room temperature and 77K is due mainly to an increased matrix friction stress.

The observed increase (of about 5%) in elastic modulus with heat treatment for both composite systems at both testing temperatures is initially surprising. After all, the heat treatments would be expected to encourage in one case an oxidation reaction and in the other the formation of Al₄C₃ at the interfaces, both of which would normally be expected to be detrimental to the bond strength. It is also intriguing that the changes in modulus with heat treatment are not reflected in corresponding changes in proof stress. The Al-Mg/SiC_p^{non-ox} has a disproportionately higher proof stress compared with the SiC_p^{ox} reinforced material than the difference in moduli would have led us to expect, and at

room temperature neither material shows any measurable change in proof stress after heat treatment. There is in fact a drop in the liquid nitrogen proof stress of Al-Mg/SiC_p^{non-ox} after heat treatment, although Al-Mg/SiC_p^{ox} shows no corresponding change.

We must consider the possible modifications to the reinforcement, the matrix, or the reinforcement/matrix bond, which could have caused the observed changes in mechanical behaviour:

1. The heat treatments, by promoting interfacial reactions, could be resulting in an effective increase in the volume fraction of reinforcing material. In order to achieve modulus changes of the observed magnitude, an effective volume fraction increase of about 15% would be necessary (ie from say 14% to 16%), requiring an increase in effective particle radius of about 300nm (for a uniform interphase of approximately the same elastic properties as the reinforcement).

2. The increases in modulus could be due to modifications in the matrix modulus as a result of changes in solute concentration: in both interfacial reactions some free silicon must be produced, which is likely to dissolve in the matrix, and the concentration of Mg in the matrix will be reduced in the Al-Mg/SiC_p^{ox} composite because of MgO formation at the interfaces. These solute concentration changes, or perhaps some associated precipitation of intermetallics, could change the matrix elastic modulus and hence that of the composite.

3. An improved interfacial bond after heat treatment could restore the moduli to values near to those predicted. To explain the magnitude of the observed changes, this would require that the bonding prior to heat treatment be negligible for this non-industrial alloy, but substantially improved by interfacial reaction. Although this is contrary to the received wisdom of the MMC world, it is clearly possible that either an array of "keying-in" interfacial precipitates, or some limited interfacial reactive or diffusive region, might actually strengthen the interfacial bond.

We shall now turn to the TEM observations to determine which of these possible explanations for the mechanical data is appropriate.

TEM CHARACTERISATION OF THE METAL/CERAMIC INTERFACES

The metal/ceramic interfaces in Al-Mg/SiC_p^{non-ox} displayed the already noted "cleanliness" of other spray-deposited aluminium-based composites; it was impossible to detect any interfacial precipitation of intermetallics³, amorphous interlayer¹⁰, or Al₄C₃⁴, though such reaction products have been observed in similar composites made by other routes. The interfaces in the as produced Al-Mg/SiC_p^{ox} composite exhibited an irregular zone (between 10 and 30 nm thick) of mixed microcrystalline and amorphous material between the SiC and the matrix. Dark field imaging (e.g. figure 2a) demonstrated that the microcrystals were randomly oriented.

Turning now to the interfacial morphology of the heat-treated Al-Mg/SiC_p^{ox} composite we see a substantial change. Figure 3a is a dark field micrograph highlighting an array of small precipitates at a SiC/aluminium interface. These crystals, whose reflections are consistent with those of MgO and may be assumed to be this oxide³, now had an orientation relationship with the SiC, which was demonstrated by the way that small tilts tended to alternately strengthen the contrast in the MgO or in the SiC for a given aperture position. The change in weak beam contrast of the SiC at the base of the MgO particles indicates local strains associated with their formation.

Figure 3b is a dark field micrograph of the same interface, obtained using the dark field imaging technique described by Withers et al¹⁰. The method consists in taking long exposure dark field micrographs at a series of aperture positions in diffraction space that does not coincide with an Al or SiC systematic but could be expected to intersect the ring pattern associated with any amorphous or microcrystalline phase. In this way, an interphase as thin as about 5Å can be detected, even though its associated ring pattern may not be visible in the diffraction pattern. The contrast at the interface in figure 3b demonstrates that there is now, after the heat treatment, an amorphous layer at the SiC/matrix interface of a uniform thickness of about 2nm. The fact that the contrast is undisturbed by the presence of the MgO particles indicates both that the interlayer is continuous and that it lies between the SiC and the MgO. This demonstrates that the orientation relationship between the microcrystals and the SiC cannot be crystallographic and must instead be morphological (a flat crystal face preferring to lie on a flat SiC surface).

Clearly, the development of the interfacial morphology between the as produced and heat treated Al-Mg/SiC_p^{ox} is inconsistent with the 300nm increase in the effective SiC radius necessary to account for the observed increase in composite modulus. Similarly, the maximum change in the Si and Mg concentration as a result of the disappearance of the original amorphous oxide layer is less

than 0.3%, which would not be expected to produce modulus changes of a suitable magnitude⁸. It seems therefore that we must attach the increase in elastic modulus of this composite to a strengthened interfacial bond. It is difficult to see how the MgO crystals could actually improve the interfacial bond strength, given that they are separated from the SiC particles by a thin amorphous layer. We thus propose that the required increase in bond strength is associated with the amorphous layer itself, which cannot thus simply be remanent SiO₂ but must instead indicate some interactive diffusion process. This proposal, though capable of explaining the mechanical behaviour and consistent with our TEM data, requires corroboration, perhaps through analysis of the interlayer, though this would be difficult.

Figure 4 is a dark field micrograph of a tilted interface in Al-Mg/SiC_p^{non-ox}, showing interfacial crystals (probably Al₄C₃) growing into the matrix from the SiC surface. In this particular area reaction products were observed to a distance of about 300nm from the interface (though these were at variable orientations and hence invisible in the micrograph shown, where only those crystallites with an orientation related to that of the underlying SiC are in contrast). However, the thickness of the interaction zone was found to be very variable and usually much less than 300nm. It is interesting that the SiC is heavily stressed beneath particle A and that no amorphous interlayer was found at this or any other interface examined; these facts, together with the tendency for an orientation relationship, suggest a strong bond between the particles (which are "keyed in" to the matrix) and the SiC.

Other interfacial crystals were observed to penetrate the SiC surface, thus enhancing this improvement in load transfer. Examples of such particles are shown in figure 5a, where again we note local deformation of the SiC particles, this time sufficient to cause cracking of the SiC. This is demonstrated by figure 5b where we see the fringes which are typical of such cracks. In figure 5b we can also note that the Al is locally very heavily dislocated, in this case because of an extended zone of reaction product in the matrix adjacent to the SiC. For Al-Mg/SiC_p^{non-ox}, we therefore have a clear picture of interfacial products growing both out from and into the SiC, thereby enhancing load transfer at the interface and, through the cracking of the SiC, providing initiation sites for local failure. Such cracking thus also provides an explanation for the lower proof stress at liquid nitrogen temperatures exhibited by the Al-Mg/SiC_p^{non-ox} once it has been heat treated.

Our TEM results as a whole point strongly to mechanism 3 alone as an explanation for the increased modulus after heat treatment in the material containing oxidised SiC, but to a combination of mechanisms 1 and 3 for the composite containing clean SiC particles. It remains unclear why the two interfacial interactions start so differently. However, once a continuous amorphous interaction zone has been established (as is observed for Al-Mg/SiC_p^{non-ox}) further localised reactions would be inhibited in a manner analogous to the way in which an oxidation reaction can be passivated by promoting an initially fast reaction.

CONCLUSIONS

Using suitable heat treatments, we have been able to modify the morphology and the associated bond strength of the metal/ceramic interfaces in spray deposited Al-Mg- based composites reinforced with SiC_p^{ox} and SiC_p^{non-ox}. The corresponding changes in mechanical properties, specifically the unexpected increase in elastic modulus after heat treatment, can be interpreted only in terms of there being an increased bond strength from the two interfacial reactions. TEM characterisation of these interfaces suggests two separate mechanisms for this improved bond strength: in Al-Mg/SiC_p^{non-ox} reaction products (probably Al₄C₃) grow both into the SiC and out into the matrix, allowing a "keying in" mechanism for increased bond strength; in the SiC_p^{ox}-reinforced composite, this reaction is prevented and the improved bond strength seems to be associated with the formation of a thin amorphous layer at the interface. While there are advantages in improving the load transfer behaviour of the interface by either of these mechanisms, the "keying in" mechanism has the disadvantage of embrittling the particles.

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Figure 1 - An experimental stress vs strain curve for Al-Mg/SiC_p^{ox}. Measurement of the elastic modulus at a is difficult because the composite microyields from a very low applied load. Initial unloading curves (b) give more useful results, but low load fatigue cycles (c-d) allow the most accurate and consistent measurements of the modulus.

Figure 2 - Darkfield micrograph of a microcrystalline/amorphous layer in as produced Al-Mg/SiC_p^{ox} (see text).

Figure 3a MgO crystals at the metal/ceramic interface in heat-treated Al-Mg/SiC^{ox}. Note the slight strain contrast in the SiC under each crystal.

Figure 3b A thin amorphous layer at the same interface. The fact that there is no change in the contrast of this layer adjacent to the MgO particles indicates that the layer lies in between the particles and the MgO (see text).

Figure 4 Reaction product growing out into the matrix at the interface in heat-treated Al-Mg/SiC^{non-ox}, and into the SiC at A

Figure 5 Reaction product growing into the SiC (a) crystals in strong contrast.

(b) associated cracking of the SiC particles is indicated by the α -fringes at A.